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Ecosystems of Innovation and Virtual-physical Interactions

UPDATED Abstract

**Data for Social Equity in the AI Era:
A Global Perspective of National Strategies and Challenges of
Transformation**

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Data for Social Equity in the AI Era? A Global Perspective of National AI Strategies and Challenges of Transformation

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This paper examines the new role of public management in safeguarding and enhancing social equity in the era of artificial intelligence (AI). AI supported by data science with its technological power and promises is well perceived as a solution to tackle global issues and dynamic societal threats including social injustice and inequity. However, to what extent it is really deployed and adopted by governments around the world for such noble purposes remains a question to be examined empirically.

In this regard, taking a global perspective, this study would first conduct content analysis of national strategies on AI of all major countries to assess their devotion and readiness in protecting social equity in the AI era. Learning from the literature of e-government, disruptive technologies, and paradigms of public management and strategic public leadership (Dunleavy et al. 2005; Lane & Wallis 2009; Radu 2021; Ulnicane et al 2021; Wong & Welch 2004), it would then develop a theoretical framework to identify the challenges for policymakers in the AI era and the strategic leadership required in the transformation. In the final part, it would conclude with selected case studies of best and non-desirable practices among countries surveyed in the first part to produce actionable lessons for scholars and practitioners for insights and future studies. Those cases would represent regions across the East and the West including the North America, Asia and Europe,

With the rapid advancement and progress of data science including AI and Big Data technologies, there is little doubt that data will have an unprecedented impact on societies, economies, and governments. Among them is the effect in terms of job disruption through automation and the ways public services are designed and delivered. Both of them have serious implications on social equity in the public sector (Ford 2021). Although the ideal state of data science is always taken as win-win for all, its promised returns to society should never be taken for granted or assumed to be accomplished effortlessly and automatically. The enabling factors in terms of good practices of policy, governance, and management are often less emphasized in the current policy discussion and public discourse.

One of the important findings from our study is that according to the national strategies of major countries so far there are limited solutions/proposals to overcome challenges of equity (mainly focused on equal data sharing/access) and very few analyses or report on how AI measures bring impact on social equity. There are concerns about understudied issues and insignificant budget and more attention on state-society interaction, public consultation, and action fostering the approach to social equity is necessary. AI for good to all in the society is the ideal outcome of AI implementation but it is taken for granted that the AI-induced transition specifically for social good is accomplished automatically and effortlessly. The conventional public management hinders the development of AI and generalization of AI solutions. Meanwhile, concerns of public management and job disruption during the AI-induced transition are pressing to be handled by the governments, especially with rapid advancement of AI technology. However, coverage of social equity in the national AI strategies is minimal, which hinted the lack of consideration of challenges of approaching social equity through public management in the AI era.

This proposed paper should fill this gap in the literature. Despite the global vision of “Data for Social Good” or “AI for Social Good”, the progress of data science without corresponding policy packages and reforms would easily lead to deeper social inequities – “Digital Divide” or “AI Divide” in specific between the data-rich and AI-advance countries and the data-poor and AI-lagged countries. Policymakers must work hard to ensure those enabling factors in governance of data and disruptive technologies including cultural, structural, and institutional changes are in place for assuring the arrival of data science will turn the potential risk and threats into real opportunities and social good (Holzmeyer 2021; Taeihagh 2021; Wong 2020). While there is a considerable amount of research on the impact of data science and AI on economic growth and innovation, there is relatively less research on what public management and policy should do on “Data for Social Equity” to avoid the classic trade-off between equity and growth (Frederickson 1990; Guy & McCandless 2021). The cost of not paying serious attention to data science disruption can be high as it would mean the possibility of not being able to have digital transformation to a data-driven society. In the absence of equity and fairness, the goals of “Data for Social Good” to benefit and empower all people can be severely compromised. All three authors are affiliated with the Data Science and Policy Studies (DSPS) of the Faculty of Social Science, the Chinese University of Hong Kong. The profile and diversity of the team serve well in attaining the objectives of the paper.

Keywords:

Artificial Intelligence, Data for Social Good, AI for Social Good, Digital Divide, Digital Governance, Digital Transformation, Disruptive Technology, Future of Work, Public Management, Social Equity, Strategic Public Leadership,

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